

Title: flower space: Exploring the feature space manifold of a GAN

Name: Dave MacDonald

Affiliation: founder of Toronto AI (a large meetup group)

ABSTRACT:

We use a Deep Convolutional Wasserstein Generative Adversarial Network (DCWGAN) to generate high resolution images of flowers from feature coordinates. We explore the feature space manifold around these coordinates using several methods: first, we explore the effect of modifying individual feature dimensions and second, we explore automated navigation across the manifold using a form of nearest neighbor path interpolation.

Image generation using a Generative Adversarial Network uses two neural networks in an adversarial game to produce an image. The generator neural network attempts to produce sample images from a feature vector to be mistaken as being indistinguishable from the training set according to the critic neural network. During training, the critic improves its ability to distinguish training samples from the generated samples. Our work explores the manifold created by the feature vectors given to the generator.

AIM:

To visually explore a feature space manifold inside a neural network.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

We use a deep convolutional encoder to learn a feature space representation of training images of flowers. This is combined with a Wasserstein GAN (WGAN) to generate high resolution images of imagined flowers from the feature space representation. We apply pixel normalization and weight normalization to stabilize training. The output of the GAN - the imagined flower images - are then displayed to a page that allows for real-time navigation across the manifold.

KEYWORDS:

GAN; WGAN; DCGAN; DCWGAN; Generative Adversarial Network; Neural Network; Flowers; Latent space; Feature space; Wasserstein; Deep Learning; Convolutional

BIOGRAPHY:

Dave MacDonald founded the Toronto AI meetup group in 2017 that grew to over 1800 members that year. He recently organised a free AI Summit at the SAS institute with 5 speakers, and regularly teaches workshops on TensorFlow through the Toronto AI group. He works at Receptiviti as a senior machine learning engineer.